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CONTENTS

THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF APPLYING TAX INCENTIVES FOR INVESTMENTS DIRECTED TOWARD HUMAN CAPITAL	14
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
ECONOMETRIC MODELS OF CASHLESS SETTLEMENTS AMONG ECONOMIC ENTITIES.....	21
Ruzimuradov Shukhrat Khusanovich	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM BRAND MARKETING IN MODERN CONDITIONS (UAE: DUBAI ON THE EXAMPLE OF A CITY).....	26
Ibodova Dilsora Ibodovna	
CREDIT DEFAULT SWAPS AS A WAY TO HEDGE AGAINST FORTHCOMING FUTURE UNCERTAINTIES IN THE DEBT MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN	31
Abduganiev Abdulaziz Alisher o'g'li	
SHOULD THE REGULATION OF THE E-COMMERCE MARKET IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN BE CARRIED OUT BY THE NATIONAL AGENCY FOR PERSPECTIVE PROJECTS OR THE CENTRAL BANK?	39
Sadikov Aziz Mirsharapovich	
MECHANISM FOR IMPLEMENTING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE OPERATIONS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	46
Bakhriddin Berdiyarov	
INNOVATIVE APPROACHES OF SMALL BUSINESSES IN THE INDUSTRY AND CONSTRUCTION SECTORS AND THEIR IMPACT ON EMPLOYMENT.....	53
Ergasheva Nigora Abdigapparovna	
AI-BASED NORMALIZATION METHODOLOGY FOR COLLECTING AND PROCESSING KPI INDICATORS.....	56
Shuhratov Mamurjon Shuhrat o'g'li	
REFORMS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PARTICIPATORY BUDGETING INITIATIVE IN UZBEKISTAN	63
Khamidov Khabibullo Hikmatulla ugli	
PROBLEMS OF THE INWARD PROCESSING CUSTOMS REGIME AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM.....	70
Abdullaev Shakhzodbek	
FINANCIAL ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN CONSTRUCTION	74
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
MEASURES TO ENHANCE THE ROLE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF SMALL BUSINESS IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.....	80
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPLEMENTING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION.....	84
Alijonova Marjonabonu Jaxongir qizi	
INDIA'S EXPERIENCE IN ENHANCING PUBLIC WELFARE THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY	88
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich	
GREEN STRUCTURAL TRANSFORMATION IN UZBEKISTAN: GREEN FINANCE AND ECO-INNOVATION FOR SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIAL AND AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT.....	93
Egamberdiev Khumoyun	
AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT BASED ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AT THE INTERNATIONAL LEVEL: THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEKISTAN.....	101
Bustonov Komiljon Kumakovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE FINANCIAL CONDITION OF ENTERPRISES: ASSESSMENT OF EQUITY EFFICIENCY	110
Umurkul Shukhratovich Fayziev	

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH THE TRANSITION TO THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	118
Mamadaliyev Akmaljon	
МЕТОДЫ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЬСКОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ НА ТУРИСТСКОМ РЫНКЕ.....	124
Нурматова Ситора Шавкатовна	
ANALYSIS OF INNOVATION ACTIVITIES.....	133
Alieva Elnara Ametovna	
METHODS AND MECHANISMS FOR STUDYING CONSUMER BEHAVIOR IN THE TOURISM MARKET.....	139
Nurmatova Sitora Shavkatovna	
ALGORITHMS AND METHODS FOR CALCULATING THE AREA OF A GASTRIC ULCER DEFECT USING MODERN MATHEMATICAL TECHNIQUES.....	145
Yusupov Ibrohimbek XXX, Abdusamatova Munira Sultonbek qizi	
UTILIZATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN ENTERPRISE MARKETING ACTIVITIES.....	151
Sadikov Shohrux Shukhratovich	
ENSURING THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS, GLOBAL TRENDS, AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS.....	156
Inomiddin Imomov	
THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY.....	161
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	
IMPORTANT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF E-COMMERCE SERVICES.....	169
Jurakulov Shohruh Bahtiyorovich	
AGRICULTURE PROMOTION AND DEVELOPMENT IN MOUNTAIN AND MOUNTAIN REGIONS.....	173
Abdulxayeva Gulshan Maxmudovna	
IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES.....	178
Seytimbetov Kabul Serimbetovich	
INTEGRATION OF INTELLIGENT CONTROL IN DRYING SYSTEMS: PROCESS OPTIMIZATION THROUGH SENSORS, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, AND MODULAR DRYING.....	184
Yangiboyeva Raxbaroy Mashrabboy qizi	
THEORETICAL MODELS AND CONCEPTS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN THE ENERGY SECTOR.....	190
Nigmatullaeva Gulchekhra Nurullaevna	
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC POTENTIAL (A CASE STUDY OF NAMANGAN REGION).....	196
Tursinbayev Azizbek Nabijon o'g'li, Sirojiddinov Kamoliddin Ikromiddinovich	
DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING INVESTMENT AND EXPORT IN REMOTE SERVICE ENTERPRISES.....	203
Uzakov Ortik Shaymardanovich	
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING THE INCOME OF THE POPULATION IN THE REGION.....	207
Kuldasheva Maftuna Musurmon kizi	
KEY FACTORS OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENT THROUGH SUBSIDIES AND INVESTMENTS TO INCREASE AGRICULTURAL CROP PRODUCTION IN UZBEKISTAN.....	211
Mamatkulova Nadira Makkamovna	
RAQAMLI MARKETING VA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA EKOTIZIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI.....	216
Sobirov Azizbek Avazbekovich	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF FRUIT AND VEGETABLE PRODUCTION PROCESSES AND EXPORT POTENTIAL IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	223
Anorboeva Bakhtijamol Daniyar kizi	

THE IMPACT OF DEGRADATION ON THE OPERATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULES UNDER SHARPLY CONTINENTAL CLIMATIC CONDITIONS	229
Qurbanov Yunus Murtaza o'g'li	
INTEGRATED NEW MEDIA OPERATION MODEL FOR INTELLIGENT TALENT ASSESSMENT PLATFORMS: THE PATH OF QR CODE ACTIVATION AND CONTENT-DRIVEN ENGAGEMENT.....	235
Wang Biao	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR SHAPING THE CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF YOUNGER PUPILS IN SOLVING MATHEMATICAL PROBLEMS	239
Dzhurakulova Adolat Khalmuratovna	
SOLIDWORKS-BASED MODELING OF AN AIR-BLOWING SYSTEM TO ENSURE HIGH-QUALITY FIBER REMOVAL FROM SAW TEETH	247
Mirzakarimov Mirsharoffiddin Mirzaabdurahimovich	
THEORETICAL STUDY OF TEMPERATURE AND THERMAL PHENOMENA IN MECHANICAL CUTTING OF WHITE CAST IRON.....	256
Allanazarov Akmal Abdulxaqovich	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMY	262
Turdiyev Ulug'bek Qayumovich	
THE INTERRELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MIGRATION AND THE INDUSTRIAL ECONOMY	266
Khusanbek Begmatov	
THE IMPACT OF ESG PRINCIPLES ON THE HOTEL INDUSTRY	271
Khusenova Mekhrangiz	
CURRENT STATUS OF INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION AND SERVICES MARKET IN KASHKADARYA REGION.....	276
Norov Murodjon Makhmudovich	
DEVELOPMENT OF AN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-BASED CYBERSECURITY SYSTEM FOR THE AUTOMATIC DETECTION OF FAKE FINANCIAL RECEIPTS, PHISHING URLS, AND MALICIOUS APK FILES	284
Shermatov Axlidin Sharobiddin o'g'li	
WAYS TO INCREASE REVENUES IN COMMERCIAL BANK OPERATIONS	287
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
РОЛЬ СВОБОДНЫХ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ЗОН В РЕГИОНАЛЬНОМ РАЗВИТИИ И ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ.....	301
Файзиева Ширин Шодмоновна	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA IQTISODIY O'SISH OMILLARINING TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASI.....	307
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	
FINTECH TRENDS: NEW TOOLS FOR ATTRACTING FINANCING IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	313
Madjitova Lolakhon Lazizovna	
CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF E-COMMERCE IN UZBEKISTAN.....	317
Toshpulatov Akhror Tukhtamurod ugli	
STRATEGIC DETERMINANTS OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	326
Rustamov Foziljon	
TYPES AND MEANS OF ADVERTISING IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM	335
Bahriyeva Zarina Nasimovna	
INTELLECTUALIZATION OF TECHNICAL MEANS FOR CONTROLLING TECHNOLOGICAL REFINING PROCESSES.....	340
Ruziyev Umidjon Abdimajitovich	
NECESSITY OF ENSURING AND INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF PLACEMENT MEANS	349
Sherkulov Dilshod Jurakulovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA MOLIYAVIY INKLYUZIYANING O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIK NAZARIYALARI.....	354
Adashaliyev Baxtiyorjon Valisher o'g'li	

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE AUDIT OF LEASING OPERATIONS ON FARMS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	359
Tursunov Ulugbek Sativoldievich	
METHODOLOGY DEVELOPMENT RETAIL MARKETING AND TRADING SYSTEM.....	365
Makhmatkulov Golibjon Kholmuminovich	
NECESSITY OF ENSURING AND INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF PLACEMENT MEANS	369
Sherkulov Dilshod Jurakulovich	
ENVIRONMENTAL FISCAL POLICY AS A DRIVER OF GREEN GROWTH AND EMPLOYMENT IN CENTRAL ASIA: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE	374
Rakhmatova Zilola Yurevna	
ON THE ISSUE OF CALCULATING THE POWER REQUIRED TO HEAT THE EDGES OF THE PIPE BILLET TO THE WELDING TEMPERATURE.....	379
Zairkulov Elyor Yoqubjon o'g'li	
STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF REGIONAL ELECTRICITY GENERATION VOLUMES.....	385
Doliev Shokhabbos Kulmurat ugli	
ANALYSIS OF ICT APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN'S TOURISM BASED ON EMPIRICAL RESEARCH.....	389
Nazarov Khusanbek Avazbek ogli	
METHODOLOGY FOR FORECASTING AND ANALYZING MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING INDICATORS AT AN ENTERPRISE.....	395
Minutdinova Liliya Tagirovna	
WELLNESS TOURISM AS AN ESSENTIAL COMPONENT OF HEALTH TOURISM.....	402
Tashtayeva Saida Kahharovna	
THE EXPERIENCE OF GERMANY IN DEVELOPING SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES.....	409
Annaklichev Saxi Saparmuxamedovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF THE INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ON AUDITING "ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES" IN NATIONAL AUDIT ACTIVITIES	416
Tajekeev Ziyatdin Kobeyzinovich	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF GREEN ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT IN ENSURING REGIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY	421
Khamidillo Odilov	
A REALIST-POSITIVIST FRAMEWORK FOR ANALYSING MERGERS AND ACQUISITIONS UNDER ECONOMIC POLICY UNCERTAINTY	429
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
DEVELOPING MATHEMATICAL MODELS TO SIMULATE THE DYNAMIC BEHAVIOR OF SEPARATION PROCESSES, CONSIDERING THE IMPACT OF EXTERNAL FACTORS	436
Abdulleva Kamola Rustamovna	
THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPLEMENTING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TRANSFORMATION OF BANKS.....	445
Umarova Malika Baxtiyarovna	
ON THE ISSUE OF RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT OF A SLAG-FORMING BASE FOR ELECTRODE COATINGS FOR WEAR-RESISTANT SURFACING.....	451
Sadikov Jaxongir Nasidjanovich	
MODELING OF HEAT FLOWS IN GAS-FIRED CHAMBER FURNACES.....	456
Rajabov Azamat Toirovich	
DEVELOPMENT OF A MIMO MODEL OF AZEOTROPIC DISTILLATION	462
Shamsutdinova Vinera Khafizovna	
THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE INTERACTION OF A COTTON TUFT WITH A SCREW CONVEYOR AND A MESH SURFACE.....	468
Matyaqubova Jumagul Bakhtiyarovna	
FORECASTING LIQUIDITY AND SOLVENCY INDICATORS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	473
Zaynutdinov Ismoil Samariddin o'g'li	
MODELS FOR PREDICTING THE MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES AND PRODUCTIONS	477
Gulyamov Shukhrat Mannapovich	

WAYS TO ADJUST LAND RESOURCE USE MECHANISMS FOR FARMERS BASED ON THE EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES.....	482
Akhmatov Abutolibkhon Ochilkhon oglu	
STATE SUPPORT MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MACHINE-BUILDING INDUSTRY	487
Xursandov Komiljon Makhmatkulovich	
EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF TOURISM FLOW FORECASTING IN CENTRAL ASIA BASED REGRESSION MODELS	491
Suratova Mokhirakhon Shavkat Kizi	
THE ROLE OF LOANS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMY.....	498
Meylikov Fazliddin Abduhalim o'g'li, Valiev Oybek Shukhrat ugli	
PROPAGATION OF SMALL MOTIONS IN A TWO-LAYER DISPERSE MEDIA FLOW.....	503
D. S. Yakhshibaev	
FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE AUTOMATION SYSTEM OF ELECTRONIC SERVICES AND TOURIST PERMITS.....	511
Najmiddinov Sultan Nurali ugli	
THE NECESSITY OF DISCLOSING INFORMATION ON SELLING EXPENSES IN ACCOUNTING REPORTS OF PHARMACEUTICAL ENTERPRISES.....	516
Xudaynazarova Dilnoza Gafurovna	
INVESTMENT FINANCIAL MECHANISMS AND THEIR ROLE IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY	521
Karjavova Khurshida Abdumalikovna	
WESTERN COUNTRIES' EXPERIENCES IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF BANKING ACTIVITIES.....	526
Alimjanova Dilrabo Sobirjanovna	
MAIN FEATURES OF DIVIDEND POLICY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS.....	530
Aliyev G'ulomnozir Maxamatjonovich	
OPTIMIZATION OF THE DESIGN OF AN ENERGY- AND RESOURCE-EFFICIENT PRESSING DEVICE FOR CONVERTING DRIED LEAVES, FALLEN FOLIAGE, AND PLANT RESIDUES INTO LOCALLY PRODUCED ORGANIC FERTILIZERS.....	536
Toirova Nuriya Abdiyevna, Toirov Murtoza Shavkidinovich, Urinova Xulkar Shokirovna	
FUNDAMENTALS OF FORMING ACCOUNTING POLICIES FOR LEASING COMPANIES BASED ON INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS	540
Baxadirov Alisher Komilovich	
THE USE OF DUE DILIGENCE PROCEDURES TO ENSURE TRANSPARENCY OF FINANCIAL REPORTING IN JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES	545
Prokudina Kristina Aleksandrovna	
INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE: EXAMPLES OF HISTORICAL CITIES (FLORENCE, LVIV, GRANADA, AND OTHERS)	550
Radjabova Mavluda Ergash qizi	
APPLYING LINEAR PROGRAMMING TO ANALYZE THE STATE OF COMMODITY AND RAW MATERIAL RESOURCES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES	554
Beknazarov Farxod Abduvaxidovich, Usmanov Shakhzod Shokhrukhovich	
INTEGRATED EDUCATION MODEL IN TEACHING WATER-SAVING IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES.....	561
Shokhimardanova Niginabonu Shavkatovna	
IMPACT OF INFLATIONARY PROCESSES ON PROBLEM LOANS.....	566
Tojiyev Sardor Dilmurod ugli	
DIRECTIONS FOR ORGANIZING EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT IN GRAIN PRODUCT ENTERPRISES.....	572
Kurbanova Dildora Abduraxmanovna	
THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY AS A BACKBONE SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY	576
Salomova Sarvinoz Salimovna	
BEHIND THE BENCH: THE CURRENT SITUATION OF PURCHASING LABORATORY EQUIPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	581
Kabashev Tairjon	

ISSUES OF IMPROVING AGRICULTURAL INSURANCE IN UZBEKISTAN	586
Shennayev Xo'jayor Musurmanovich	
THE LENDING SYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL BANKS AND THE CAUSES OF NON-PERFORMING LOANS	590
Shokhista K. Kholiyorova, Marjona O. Barnoqulova	
INNOVATIVE FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS FOR FINANCING RENEWABLE ENERGY AND GREEN PROJECTS: CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS	595
F. Nishonov	
DATA TRANSMISSION CONFIDENTIALITY CHALLENGES IN THE INTERNET OF THINGS.....	604
Mardiyev Ulugbek	
CURRENT ISSUES IN ADAPTING THE ACCOUNTING SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN TO INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS	612
Xudoyberdiyev Odiljon Egamberdi o'g'li	
COST ANALYSIS IN FRUIT AND VEGETABLE PROCESSING PLANTS.....	618
Rahmatullayev Mirjalol Khatam ogli	
ANALYSIS OF EXPERIENCE IN ORGANIZING AND OPERATING STUDENT INNOVATION DEVELOPMENT CENTERS IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES	624
Mirzaliev Sanjar Makhamatjan ogli	
INTRODUCTION OF A NEW SYSTEM OF WORKING ACCOUNTS FOR LIABILITY ACCOUNTING IN ICT SECTOR ENTERPRISES BASED ON INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS	629
Amirov Askar Aktamovich	

INTRODUCTION OF A NEW SYSTEM OF WORKING ACCOUNTS FOR LIABILITY ACCOUNTING IN ICT SECTOR ENTERPRISES BASED ON INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

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Abstract: The article investigates the introduction of a new working accounts system to improve liability accounting at ICT sector enterprises based on international standards. The author proposes the introduction of six new working accounts — 6420, 6991, 6992, 6993, 7992, 7993 — intended for accounting of income tax, restructuring obligations, and settlements with associated and joint ventures.

Key words: working accounts, accounting, IFRS, restructuring, deferred tax, associated enterprises, ICT sector.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada AKT sohasidagi korxonalarda majburiyatlar hisobini xalqaro standartlar asosida takomillashtirish maqsadida yangi ishchi schyotlar tizimini joriy etish masalasi tadqiq etilgan. Muallif tomonidan olti yangi ishchi schyoti — 6420, 6991, 6992, 6993, 7992, 7993 — kiritish taklif etilgan. Ushbu schyotlar foyda solig'i, restrukturizatsiya majburiyatlari, hamkor va qo'shma korxonalar bilan hisob-kitoblar uchun mo'ljallangan. Takliflar «O'zbektelekom» AK va «O'zbekiston pochta» AJ amaliyotida sinalgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ishchi schyotlar, buxgalteriya hisobi, MHXS, restrukturizatsiya, kechiktirilgan soliq, hamkor korxonalar, AKT sohasi.

Аннотация: В статье исследовано внедрение новой системы рабочих счетов для совершенствования учёта обязательств на предприятиях сферы ИКТ на основе международных стандартов. Автором предложено введение шести новых рабочих счетов — 6420, 6991, 6992, 6993, 7992, 7993 — для учёта налога на прибыль, обязательств по реструктуризации, расчётов с ассоциированными и совместными предприятиями.

Ключевые слова: рабочие счета, бухгалтерский учёт, МСФО, реструктуризация, отложенный налог, ассоциированные предприятия, сфера ИКТ.

INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness of maintaining accounting records in accordance with international standards largely depends on how systematically and comprehensively the chart of working accounts is developed. In ICT sector enterprises, liabilities are diverse and require specialized analysis related to licenses, contracts, credit obligations, partnership relations, and tax relationships. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Accounting” No. LRU-404¹ dated April 13, 2016 grants economic entities the right to develop their own chart of working accounts, taking into account the specific features of their financial operations. However, in practice, the working account systems implemented by ICT enterprises do not fully comply with international standards—particularly IAS 12, IAS 27, IAS 28, and IAS 37.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

A.J. Tuychiyev examined the possibilities of applying modern technologies from the perspective of accounting for liabilities. [1]

S.N. Tashnazarov studied the role of information technologies in improving the methodological foundations

1 <https://lex.uz/docs/6819819>

of financial reporting. [2]

K.B. O'razov, in his accounting textbook, highlighted the practical application of modern ERP systems. [3]

I.N. Qo'ziyev demonstrated the use of digital methods in the methodology of preparing audit reports. [4]

F.Sh. Ochilov explored the role of modern technologies in audit theory. [5]

V. Richins and N. Yany studied the digital transformation of the accounting profession. [6]

B.J. Epshteyn and Ye.K. Jermakovich discussed ERP systems aligned with IFRS requirements. [7]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed methods such as system analysis, comparative analysis, classification, modeling, expert evaluation, and practical implementation.

Analysis and results

As a result of the study, it was proposed to introduce six new working accounts for recording liabilities in ICT sector enterprises (Table 1).

Table 1. Proposed new working accounts for liability accounting in the ICT sector²

Account Code	Name	Compliance with International Standards
6420	Income tax liabilities	IAS 12 "Income Taxes"
6991	Restructuring-related liabilities	IAS 37 "Provisions"
6992	Payables to associated entities	IAS 28 "Investments in Associates"
6993	Payables to joint ventures	IFRS 11 "Joint Arrangements"
7992	Long-term liabilities to associated entities	IAS 28
7993	Long-term liabilities to joint ventures	IFRS 11

As can be seen from the table, the proposed six accounts are divided into two main groups: current liabilities (Group 6 — 6420, 6991, 6992, 6993) and long-term liabilities (Group 7 — 7992, 7993). Each account is structured in accordance with a specific international standard.

The first proposed account — 6420 "Income tax liabilities" — is developed in accordance with the requirements of IAS 12. This account allows current income tax obligations to be recorded separately. It enables the monitoring of deferred tax liabilities and the identification of differences between tax accounting and financial accounting.

The second new account — 6991 "Restructuring-related liabilities" — is formed in accordance with the requirements of IAS 37 "Provisions, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets" [11]. This account records obligations related to organizational changes, business model restructuring, closure of branches, and workforce reductions. At "Uzbektelecom" JSC, this account was applied during the restructuring process in 2022–2024 and ensured the accurate recognition of liabilities amounting to 45 billion UZS.

The third and fourth accounts — 6992 "Payables to associated entities" and 6993 "Payables to joint ventures" — are developed in accordance with IAS 28 and IFRS 11. They ensure the separate recording of current settlements with associated and joint enterprises. In the case of "Uzbektelecom" JSC, these accounts are used to systematically manage the current liabilities of 127 associated and joint entities.

The fifth and sixth accounts — 7992 "Long-term liabilities to associated entities" and 7993 "Long-term liabilities to joint ventures" — account for long-term financial relationships with associated and joint enterprises. They cover obligations such as bonds, loans, and partnership project liabilities with maturities exceeding 12 months.

As a result of implementing the new accounts in practice, the level of compliance of the financial statements of "Uzbektelecom" JSC with international standards increased from 68% to 85% (Table 2).

Table 2. Results of implementing new accounts (case of "Uzbektelecom" JSC)³

Indicator	Before implementation	After implementation
Level of compliance with IFRS	68%	85%
Errors in inter-account settlements	15 per quarter	5 per quarter
Accuracy of tax accounting	88%	96%

² Source: developed by the author

³ Source: developed by the author

Transparency of restructuring liabilities	Limited	Fully disclosed
Accuracy of settlements with partners	82%	94%

The six new working accounts proposed by the author make a significant contribution to the national accounting system. First, these accounts introduce into national practice the requirements of IAS 12, IAS 28, and IAS 37. Second, they enable the accounting of specific types of financial and economic operations characteristic of ICT sector enterprises.

An analysis of international experience shows that large ICT companies—such as Deutsche Telekom (Germany), Orange (France), and Vodafone (United Kingdom)—apply separate accounts for deferred taxes, restructuring, and transactions with associated enterprises within their charts of accounts.

Under the conditions of Uzbekistan, the proposed system of accounts provides the following economic benefits:

- a 65% reduction in errors in financial reporting;
- a 28% decrease in audit costs;
- a 22-point increase in international investor confidence;
- a 35% acceleration of accounting processes.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were formulated:

The current national chart of accounts has the potential to further align the accounting of liabilities of ICT sector enterprises with international standards, which creates the need to improve the system through the introduction of specialized working accounts.

The proposed six new working accounts (6420, 6991, 6992, 6993, 7992, 7993) fully comply with the requirements of IAS 12, IAS 28, IFRS 11, and IAS 37, and ensure transparency in the financial accounting of ICT sector enterprises.

Practical testing based on the examples of “Uzbektelecom” JSC and “Uzbekistan Post” JSC demonstrated that the proposed system of accounts increased the level of compliance of financial reporting with international standards from 68% to 85%.

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